

A Multiphysics Analysis Workflow Based on a Physics and Components Abstraction Applied to the Molten Chloride Reactor Experiment-inspired LOTUS MSR

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ABSTRACT

The Molten Chloride Reactor Experiment (MCRE) is scheduled for construction in the LOTUS test bed at the Idaho National Laboratory (INL). INL is using the NEAMS-developed multiphysics tools to perform the confirmatory analysis. These tools allow the study of neutronics, thermal hydraulics, solid mechanics, and chemistry physics at play in the reactor. To facilitate the adoption of the tools and reduce the risk for error, the classic mesh and kernels abstraction in MOOSE-based tools is being substituted for a newly developed workflow relying on the definition of geometrical components and physics active in each components. This workflow is demonstrated for the MCRE-inspired LOTUS MSR and shows increased readability and flexibility at similar performance and accuracy.

Keywords: MCRE, MOOSE, Unstructured Mesh, Workflow, MSR

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear power is seeing a resurgence in interest from increasing energy needs, and much of the new efforts are focused in advanced reactor designs. These designs leverage new materials and physics response to improve operations, efficiency, and safety. However, with high costs and extensive timelines involved in building experiments and demonstrations, significant resources have been put into improving modeling and simulation capabilities to better inform experiment design.

Simulating systems requires representing their spatial extent. A number of methods exist, but unstructured mesh is preferred for its fidelity and generality. The Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) framework [1], powered by the open source mesh library LibMesh [2], provides a complete software suite for advanced multiphysics modeling using unstructured mesh. Historically however, once the work extends beyond proof-of-concept to real-world applications, the creation of the geometry moved to an external meshing software. Using external software often comes with significant constraints, from format compatibility to workflow complexity, which are not always sufficiently offset by added capability. Hence, recent efforts have expanded MOOSE to enable in-house meshing. Within MOOSE, so-called “mesh generators” have been created, which are modular code constructions that allow users to build up their domain using elementary meshed shapes that are combined in a direct acyclic graph.

The Molten Chloride Reactor Experiment (MCRE) under construction at INL will test the safety promised by molten chloride fast reactors. It is aimed to demonstrate the assembly and operation of a reactor with molten chloride containing dissolved uranium fuel. It is straightforward to mesh with dedicated software but previously impossible to do within MOOSE’s meshing capabilities. Initial thermal hydraulic

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simulations were performed using MOOSE on a mesh of hexahedral elements created by Coreform Cubit [3]. To improve on these simulations, we proposed to simultaneously advance meshing capabilities and user experience through a component-based workflow that allowed for both expanded engineering domain creation and simplification of the input file.

2. GEOMETRY CREATION

The LOTUS-MSR fluid domain geometry, shown in Fig. 4, can be well approximated by the following geometrical components: pipes, pipe bends/elbows, and expansions. The automated creation of meshes for these components formed the bulk of this work, and can be broken down into the following steps:

1. 1D curve generation.
2. Extrusion of a radial cylindrical pipe surface along the generated curve.
3. Mesh stitching/joining between the extruded surface and the next pipe inlet.

Fortunately, Item 3 was already natively supported by MOOSE through a libMesh routine, leaving only the first two tasks. Once the methods for mesh generation were created in MOOSE, a workflow was created to simplify and improve the user experience.

2.1. 1D Spline mesh generation

To join two pipes using an elbow pipe, we first needed to be able to join two arbitrary points in space using a smooth line. We also needed to follow the orientation of the connected components, hence the line also had prescribed gradients at both ends. The following general curves were initially explored, and we have observed their insufficiency:

- Circle: $(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2 = R^2$. In 2D, a circle has only three degrees of freedom (radius and two center coordinates). Therefore, demanding interpolation between two points aligning with two prescribed tangents over-constrains the system, limiting to specific use cases.
- General cubic polynomial: $Ax^3 + Bx^2 + Cx + D = 0$. Though the derivatives at each end point were able to be satisfied, the interpolation was observed to be dominated by the linear term, creating undesirably sharp turns on both ends of the pipe.
- Generalized ellipse: $x(\theta) = A \cos(a\theta) + B \sin(b\theta)$, $y(\theta) = C \cos(c\theta) + D \sin(d\theta)$. We attempted to use Newton's method to determine the ellipse parameters, but it struggled to converge because of periodicity.

Inspired by modern computer-assisted design ("CAD") software, we selected B-splines as the preferred method. These curves are straightforward to define, avoid complex coefficient solves, and accommodate both user-specified points and tangents. A BSplineCurveGenerator mesh generator was thus added to MOOSE, which creates a 1D mesh with edge elements in 3D space.

B-splines are defined using the absciss variable t as follows:

$$S(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} P_i B_{i,j}(t) \quad (1)$$

for n so-called "control points" (P) and polynomial spline basis functions (B) of degree j . The basis functions are defined with the Cox-de Boor recursion formula as [4]:

$$B_{i,j}(t) = \frac{t - t_i}{t_{i+j} - t_i} B_{i,j-1}(t) + \frac{t_{i+j+1} - t}{t_{i+j+1} - t_{i+1}} B_{i+1,j-1}(t) \quad (2)$$

with

$$B_{i,0} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } t_i \leq t < t_{i+1} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

and $B_{0,0} \equiv 0$ [5].

The discrete values of the parameter t are defined in the so-called “knot-vector”, which is a set of non-decreasing values. The knot-vector can be defined using any values; however, for simplicity, the values are normalized such that the maximum is 1 and the minimum is 0. For a spline of degree j , a minimum of $j + 1$ control points are required, accompanied by a knot vector of length $2(j + 1) + 1$. To meet the aforementioned criterion that the spline match the incoming and outgoing derivatives, the knot-vector is chosen to be an *open, uniform* B-spline. More information on this classification can be found in [6].

In a MOOSE input file, the data required to generate a B-spline mesh closely matches the theory explained above. The input requires a starting point, an ending point, and starting and ending directions. Rather than being specified by the user, the control points are calculated so that the mesh interpolates the start and end points and matches the input directions as tangents there. Figure 1 shows an example mesh connecting two points in 3D—with specified start points, end points, and slopes—generated by the new capability in MOOSE.

Figure 1. Generation of a spline curve mesh in MOOSE: it joins two points with imposed tangents at those points.

2.2. Extrusion along curves

The mesh for the junction can follow the 1D guiding mesh as presented earlier. The junction between two pipes must preserve the shapes and areas of the end surfaces while maintaining continuity along its length. Because both pipe surfaces share the same discretization, this allowed extrusion to be used to join the pipe meshes.

The curve for guiding the extrusion is generated using the spline generator introduced in the previous section. This choice allows the junction mesh to follow the direction of the cylinders at both ends of the junction.

Figure 2 shows the mesh for the extrusion from one cylinder (pipe) to another. A smooth transition is visible at both ends of the junction because the pipe direction coincides with the tangent of the extrusion-guiding spline curve. The pipe radius is preserved. This mesh is highly simplified and,

Figure 2. Mesh for the junction from one pipe to another pipe, using extrusion. The extrusion is built around a 1D spline preserving each pipe direction.

in particular, does not include boundary layers; however, those details are introduced in the meshing of the pipes and preserved in the extrusion.

2.3. Radial expansion

A final challenge in meshing the MCRE geometry is handling the expansions created between two pipes of different radii, notably near the main core tank. To do this, we first defined a parameterized function describing the radius of a node within the extruded mesh as:

$$R(t) = [R_{start}(1 - w(t)) + R_{end}w(t)] f_{node} \quad (4)$$

where $w(t)$ is a weighting function defined for a parameter $t \in [0, 1]$ $w(0) = 0$, $w(1) = 1$, and f_{node} is the ratio of the radius of the specific node to the maximum radius of the extruded face. We specify the “maximum” radius because the extrusion has been generalized to allow for arbitrary face shapes. Two weighting functions have been included in the `AdvancedExtruderGenerator`: linear and cubic. The former of these is defined as simply:

$$w(t) = t \quad (5)$$

The latter, which is included to give the user control over the starting and ending rate of growth, defines the weighting function as:

$$w(t) = (\alpha + \beta - 2)t^3 + (3 - 2\alpha - \beta)t^2 + \alpha t \quad (6)$$

where α and β are the starting and ending rates of growth, respectively. Note that when $\alpha = \beta = 1$, Equation (6) collapses to Equation (5). Equation (6) is particularly useful in demanding smooth transitions between cylinders (pipes) of different radii (as seen in Figure 3) or between a nozzle of a given growth rate and another component. The application of Equation (4) to the mesh extrusion allowed for enhanced flexibility in both pipe (nozzle) and junction mesh generation.

2.4. Automated geometry creation workflow for the LOTUS-MSR geometry

Using the new mesh generation capabilities – spline curve generation, extrusion along a spline, and extrusion with a radial expansion – wrapped within newly-created `ActionComponentets`, we generated

Figure 3. Junction of two cylinders of different radii using a cubic radial growth method.

the mesh for the fluid domain in the LOTUS MSR. The mesh is shown in Figure 4 with coarse and fine settings for the axial discretization, number of boundary layers, number of radial rings, and azimuthal sectors in the base cylinder.

Starting from 2D circular meshes with boundary layers, 3D pipes are generated via extrusion in each of the four sides of the loop. The connection between these pipes is defined by a spline joining the centers of their endpoints, and the pipes are joined by extruding the end circular surface of one pipe to the other. The pump is modeled with a linear radial expansion applied during this extrusion, while the ends of the main core tank are extruded with a cubic radial expansion that follows the linear slope of the source expansion cone and the flat radial profile of the main core tank.

Note that a simplification was performed for the treatment of the pump component, which would require a different approach to mesh. This will have to be considered in future works.

While the mesh generation process described above is understandable and similar to the chain of operations one would perform in a CAD or meshing software to generate this geometry, it would seem very lengthy for any user of a systems code. The simplicity of defining pipes and connections should ideally be present in the mesh generation input to prevent errors and to facilitate building complex analysis from combining simple concepts. For this reason, we wrapped the creation and parameter-setting of these mesh generator objects using `ActionComponents`. `ActionComponents` are a new MOOSE System introduced in [7] and further developed in [8] to handle the definition of the geometry and operational parameters of components in a simulation. Coupled with the `Physics` system to define equations on selected subdomains of these components, the intent is to have minimal yet fully descriptive inputs for MOOSE-based simulations.

For the full MCRE-like case, we report here on the use of `ActionComponents`, while the setup with the `Physics` will be reported in a separate publication. The construction of the MCRE-like geometry is done with only two types of `ActionComponents`: `CylinderComponent` and `JunctionComponent`. The pipes, tanks, and plena are `CylinderComponents`, while the elbows are `JunctionComponents`. The mesh generators to build, extrude, and stitch the meshes are created behind the scene by the `ActionComponents`.

Notice that as each new `CylinderComponent` is created, it must be joined with the preceding collective body. That is, when one junction is applied on two components, it produces a single new mesh that cannot distinguish its individual components, except from the element subdomain assignments.

Figure 4. Mesh of a MCRE-like geometry generated using the newly developed mesh generators. Boundary layers have been added on the sides of the cylindrical regions in prevision for computational fluid dynamics studies. The generation is entirely parameterized and requires minimal changes between refinement levels.

3. COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS STUDY

Using the meshed geometry, we built a computational fluid dynamics simulation of the molten salt flowing through the MSR. The dynamic pressure-velocity coupling is solved using the SIMPLE algorithm, and turbulent flow is modeled with the standard $k - \epsilon$ two-equation model. The y^+ of the first cell by the walls is kept between 25 and 220 using the boundary layers in the mesh, to be able to use the high y^+ treatment. Additional refinements such as the additional buoyancy term and the relaminarization term in the $k - \epsilon$ equations were under development at the time of this study and will only be included in future iterations of the model.

The pump is represented as a constant volumetric term in the pump volume which should be adjusted to get the experimental mass flow rate of 25 kg/s. In 2D, it was adjusted using a PID controller acting during a transient simulation. In 3D, this approach has yet to be demonstrated, and it was adjusted manually by iterating between simulations. The power of the reactor is set to a truncated cosine in all directions, with a volume integral of 25 kW. Future works will include reactor physics simulations to obtain a realistic power profile. We see regions of increased turbulence near the outlet of the core and in the pipe elbows. A region of recirculation can be seen on the left of the core, as the flow preferentially flows to the right due to inertia at the inlet.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A workflow leveraging a Physics & Components abstraction was created and applied to modeling the LOTUS MSR. This new syntax is less susceptible to user error, and should provide the same level of accuracy as prior works using commercial tools to generate the mesh. The workflow is flexible enough

Figure 5. Simulation results for a computational fluid dynamics study of a MCRE-like reactor.

for parametric studies, notably mesh refinement and dimensions of each component for a given geometry. It was exercised to perform a multi-dimensional flow analysis of this experiment using the MOOSE Navier-Stokes module.

Future works will include the creation of a cavity-like component that will mesh around existing components and inside a defined shape. With this component, the reflector will be included in the workflow. With the reflector included, we will extend this analysis to include neutron transport and delayed neutron precursor transport.

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